

The Influences of Shopping Convenience, Produce Choice and Online Payment on Behavioural Intention to Use M-Commerce: The Case of Online Shoppers in Bangalore

¹ Dr. Sudarshan Seshanna, ² Dr. Hemant Kumar ³Sudharson Ramanujam

^{1&2} Professor, CMS Business School, Jain University, Bangalore, India

³ Research Scholar, Jain University, Bangalore, India

Article Info

Volume 83

Page Number: 25086 – 25096

Publication Issue:

May - June 2020

Article History

Article Received: 11 May 2020

Revised: 19 May 2020

Accepted: 29 May 2020

Publication: 12 June 2020

Abstract:

The main purpose of the study is to examine the factors that influence the usage of Mobile Commerce among the online shoppers in Bangalore. The objective of this study is verified based on the model developed. The model used as the base to check the influences of Shopping convenience, Produce choice and Online payment on Behavioural intention of the shoppers to use Mobile Commerce. Trust is considered as a mediator. The descriptive research design is applied and the respondent for the study is selected through non probabilistic judgemental sampling technique. There are 270 valid responses were considered. The collected data was analysed through Structural Equation Modelling (SEM). The result supported all the hypotheses and Trust is mediating the relationships. The study results show that the usage of Mobile Commerce is influenced by Shopping convenience, Produce choice and Online payment. The study will help the app developers and online vendors to understand the factors needs to be considered during their plan.

Keywords: M-Commerce, Bangalore, Behavioural intention, Trust

INTRODUCTION

The focus of the customers are turning towards M-Commerce because of the benefits like mobility, personalization, flexibility, easy to repeat purchase, accessibility, avoid standing in a queue, easy payment and convenience (Dong et al., 2012; Islam et al., 2011; Hossain et al., 2008; Stephen et al., 2008; Shin et al., 2002; Jiang et al., 2015; Wong et al., 2015). M-Commerce also provides the flexibility like browse, search, and compare the product features, prices on the move (Yang and Kim, 2012). M-commerce supplements E-

Commerce by allowing consumers to conduct online transactions via handheld device (Mahatanankoon, 2007).

These benefits were only partially provided by the traditional retail channels like brick and mortar stores and electronic medium. The meaning and scope of M-Commerce is borrowed from (Wang, Lin, & Luran, 2006), the meaning of M-Commerce for this study is referred to a the services provided by telecommunication and service providing companies such as emails, short message services, online music, mobile shopping, online news, play

online games, stock trading, travel planning & ticket booking, radio cabs, ordering food & drinks, mobile fortune teller, online friend finder, online auctions, buy books and mobile service. However, the statement may sound like narrow viewpoint toward M-Commerce. In large M-Commerce is a service that “empowers shoppers with the ability to gather information on the spot from multiple sources, check on product availability, special offers and alter their selection at any point along the path to purchase” (Lai et al., 2012).

India has 1170.02 million wireless telephone users with over all tele density of 89.48% (TRAI Report, January 2019). India is in 2nd position in terms of internet users (Internet world stats, 2018) and India is top ranked country in mobile data consumption (Times of India, 2017). After Jio has launched their cellular business in India the data usage has been increased and the price of mobile internet data packs has been reduced. With the evolution of Mobile technology (3G, LTE, 5G), increase in coverage of mobile network, competitive prices of smartphones & mobile internet data packs, popularity of mobile shopping is increasing all over the world (Euromonitor Research, 2013).

ASSOCHAM-Resurgent India study, 2017 - projects that M-Commerce is likely to jump to 45-50% in 2017. The first time users are contributed for the 50% of the M-Commerce sales. The M-Commerce usage in tier II and III cities in India are increasing. Among all the cities in India, people in Bangalore have reported highest preference for online shopping in Y’2016, followed by Mumbai and Delhi. In the Y’2015-2016, 69% of its population from Bangalore preferred to do e-shopping, the percentage has increased to 75% during the Y’2017.

By looking the growing popularity of the M-Commerce the merchandisers are making huge investment in the online M-Commerce business. Marketers also encouraging consumers to buy goods

and services through online; by offering discounts, coupons and loyalty points. Therefore the aim of the study is set as to identify the factors that influence the behavioural intention of the Bangalore online shoppers towards the usage of app based M-Commerce

LITERATURE REVIEW AND HYPOTHESES DEVELOPMENT

App based M-Commerce and its advantage

M-Commerce is defined as the ability to purchase goods and services anywhere and anytime through a hand held mobile device also M-Commerce provides communication-in-motion (Morris Kalliny and Michael Minor, 2006). M-Commerce is the subset of e-commerce that allows the users to perform business in a wireless mode, anywhere and anytime (Kourouthanassis et al., 2012; Chong et al., 2012). Smart phones are Application based; those applications are used for accessing all the services. (Chaffey, 2009) listed out five major benefits that Mobile connections provides to the user, those are Ubiquity, Reachability, Convenience, Security and Always-on. In addition to that location based service and user based customized service are the benefits extended by the app based M-Commerce.

Mobile Shopping Convenience (SC)

People interested to adopt a new technology if they perceive that the technology provides more convenience to their life (Hossain et al., 2008). (Stephen Burgess et al., 2008) examine convenience is the business factor that assist to maintain the relationship between Business to Consumer (B2C). (Morris Kalliny et al., 2006) study reveals that convenience factor plays a major role in M-Commerce adoption. In conventional commerce model customers are constrained by time and location, but M-Commerce provides the convenience to purchase anytime and anywhere (Tse et al., 2003). (Tang et al., 2001) states that the acceptance for M-

Commerce is keep on increasing due to the convenience and quality of service provided. The results of study by (Aminul Islam et al., 2011) on M-Commerce service in Bangladesh claims that convenience factor does not have a significant impact towards the adoption of M-commerce services, this study result are contradict to other study result. Our hypothesis as follows

H1. Higher Mobile shopping convenience will leads to higher behavioural intentions to use M-Commerce

Product Choice

Product choice (PC) refers to the decisions that consumers make with regard to **products** and services based on options like wide range of quality product, maximum product variety, broad choice of products, maximum product availability and ease of comparison shopping (Torkzadeh and Dhillon, 2002). Product choice is the most useful utilitarian factor which was not explored much in the M-Commerce perspective. Our study will helps to fill this gap.

H2. Higher Product choice will leads to higher behavioural intentions to use M-Commerce

Mobile Payment

Mobile payment (MP) is the extension of electronic payment system and it has more mobility (Ikram Dastan and CemGurler, 2016). Mobile payment is a payment system in which the mobile devices (smart phones and tablets) are used to initiate, activate and confirm any payment (Karnouskos, 2004). M-Banking, is one of the major benefit provided by the M-Commerce, which helps the users to perform their transaction activities anywhere and without any time constrain (Laukkanenet al., 2007). M-Banking provides services like mobile payment, money transfer, account checking and receiving message

about the transactions and promotional offers from banks on mobile phones (Deb et al.,2017)

H3. Mobile Payment positively influence behavioural Intention to use M-Commerce

Trust as a Mediating variable

(Sukkar et al., 2005), study states that the technology adoption models which was designed for the developed countries may not be appropriate for under developed and developing countries, trust is the basic element which needs to be considered from the consumer perspective. The trust in online shopping can be built through the customer belief that vendor has gain nothing by cheating, the required safety mechanism built in the exchange medium, by having a typical interface and easy to use (Gefen et al., 2003). Previous literature has reflected the role of Trust as a mediating variable in Data Exchange (Nicolaou et al., 2006) and Contract Enforcement (Yen et al., 2019). Trust is taken as independent variable affecting new technology adoption intention (Sreenivasan et al., 2010;Wen et al., 2011; Chong et al., 2012; Amoroso et al., 2012; Chong 2013a, b; Hanafizadeh et al., 2014; and Ingham et al., 2015), but in our study Trust is considered as mediating variable.

H4. Trust mediates the effect of Mobile Payment on the Behavioural intention to use M-Commerce

Behavioural Intention

Behavioural Intention (BI) refers to the measure of how likely an individual will perform a specific (Fishbein et al., 1975,1979; Davis et al., 1993). Factors Mobile Shopping Convenience, Product Choice and Mobile Payment may influence the Behavioural intention towards M-Commerce usage which further determines the actual usage. Thus this research proposes the following hypothesis:

H5: Behavioural intention will have a significant positive influence on actual usage of M-Commerce

Research Framework

Figure 01. represents the relationship between the 3 independent variables SC, PC and MP with dependent variable BI. One more dependent variable AU also include in the model, this will helps to determine the actual use of M-Commerce by the customers. Further, it also proposed that trust act as mediating variable between SC, PC, MP and BI. The research methodology section talks about the validation of relationships between the independent and dependent.

Figure 01. Theoretical Framework

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Participants

The study was conducted among the working professionals of Bengaluru, who have used M-Commerce services and transaction at least few times during the last one year. The reason for selection of Bengaluru as sample frame is as follows: The migrant population from other state to Bengaluru is more than 50% (Times of India, Aug'2019), this helps the researcher to identify the consumer behaviour from different states. The reason for selection of working profession as sample is they are more actively using M-Commerce rather than other sector population.

Measurement of Constructs

The proposed research framework has three independent (SC, PC and MP), one mediating (Trust) and two dependent (BI and AU) variables. Each variable is measured by survey questionnaire which was derived based on previous studies. The measurement items also adopted from previously validated studies and each variable is measured through 5 to 6 questions. Five point Likert scale is used for the measurement where 1 states as highly disagree and 5 states as highly agree

Research instrument

The data was collected through both online survey and paper based questionnaire from the representative sample. The questionnaire has contains two section, the first section captures the details about the demographic profiles of the respondents and the second section captures the details about the research variables. Initially a pilot study was conducted to check the correctness of the survey instrument, the questionnaire was distributed among 20 respondents comprises of subject expert, IT professionals, research scholars and management faculty members. Based on the pilot study result, few measurement items got modified, dropped and updated. There are 26 items were used in the final questionnaire to measure three independent variables, two dependent variables and one mediating variable.

Sampling

Non-probabilistic judgement sampling technique is used for selection of the representative sample. The questionnaire was distributed to more than 320 respondents. The online survey link was shared with 200 representative samples and 120 paper based questionnaire also distributed. The response rate was 84%, the response for paper based questionnaire (93%) is better than online (79%) survey. Total of 270 valid fully completed responses are considered for the study.

Data analysis and results

The reliability of items for different questionnaire measuring the variables in the study was assessed by calculating the coefficient alpha. Lee Cronbach in the year 1951 developed Cronbach to measure internal consistency of a scale. Cronbach alpha is used to measure the reliability of the variables and it's values are ranges between 0 to 1. Cronbach alpha is near to zero means the internal consistency

of the variable is weaker and if the value is nearer to then the internal consistency of the item in the scale is greater. An analysis of table reveals that Cronbach alpha for most of the constructs is more than 0.8 for all the constructs indicating that consistency of the instrument is quiet good and also quality of data is reliable.

Table 01: **Reliability and Descriptive Analysis**

Sn	Constructs Name	Cronbach alpha	Mean	Std	No of items
1	Convenience	0.81	4.26	0.56	6
2	Product Choice	0.85	4.37	0.56	6
3	Online Payment	0.94	4.01	1.01	5
4	Trust	0.84	3.69	0.68	6
5	Behavior intention to use	0.85	4.04	0.69	3

Source: Authors' compilation.

Discriminant validity is used to check whether the construct measures itself rather than any other constructs. This is calculated by examining by the method provided by (Fornell et al., 1981), the overlap in variance by comparing the AVE of each construct with the squared correlations among other construct. The diagonal elements in

table 02 represents Average Variance Extracted (AVE) for each construct, and the other values represents the correlation between constructs. The square root of each construct's AVE was found to be higher than its correlations with any other construct, which means that the constructs measures itself.

Table 02: **Discriminant Validity of the Constructs: Correlation Analysis**

	1	2	3	4	6
1 Convenience	1.00				
2 Product Choice	0.32	1.00			
3 Online Payment	0.19	0.16	1.00		
4 Trust	0.25	0.12	0.05	1.00	

5 Behavior intention	0.39	0.20	0.06	0.46	1.00
----------------------	------	------	------	------	-------------

Source: Authors' compilation.

Psychometric properties of the variables such as composite reliability and validity were checked.

Table 03: Psychometric properties of the variables: composite reliability and validity

	No. of Items	CR	AVE
Convenience	6	0.883	0.538
Product Choice	6	0.873	0.631
Online Payment	5	0.915	0.730
Trust	5	0.887	0.566
Behavioural Intention	3	0.911	0.774

Source: Authors' compilation.

The composite reliability of constructs ranges from .911 to 0.883. According to (Hair et al., 2014), the range between 0.70 to 0.95 are considered 'satisfactory to good'. The results shows that the CR is satisfactory to good. To evaluate convergent validity, average variance extracted (AVE) of each construct was calculated, as suggested by (Fornell et al., 1981). The AVE for all items shows convergent validity as the value exceeds 0.50. The assessment of reliability and validity of the measurement model shows that the values are satisfactory. The next step is to identify the structural model that best fits the data.

Structural Model

The theoretical model is based on good indices and bad indices. The Table shows the values of those indices.

Table 04: Model Performance

Model	Threshold
-------	-----------

	Statistics	Statistics
Npar	26.000	na
Chisq	170.428	lesser the better
DF	107.000	na
Pvalue	0.000	>.05
CFI	0.965	>.90
NNFI	0.928	.90
RMSEA	0.043	<.05
RMSEA.ci.lower	0.037	<.05
RMSEA.ci.upper	0.055	<.05
SRMR	0.048	<.05
GFI	0.926	>.90
TLI	0.957	>.90
CMIN	1.671	<3

Source: Authors' compilation.

The good indices considered are CFI, NNFI, GFI and TLI, the values are expected to be more than 0.90. All the good indices values are more than 0.90.

The bad indices are SRMR and RMSEA are expected to be less than 0.05. All indices values are closely matched. Besides CMIN should be less than 3. CMIN is close to 1.671. All these indices confirm the CFA output which has statistical validation for the theoretical structure

All the above results confirms the reliability and validity of the measurement model is within the limit and model fitness also in recommended limits. By using the AMOS software a structural model was constructed. The output from the AMOS is given in table 05.

Table 05: Results

Hypotheses	Standardized regression weights (β)	P-Value	Remarks
H1: SC \rightarrow BI	0.19	>0.001	Supported
H2: PC \rightarrow BI	0.17	0.002	Supported
H3: MP \rightarrow BI	0.33	>0.001	Supported
H5: BI \rightarrow AU	0.60	>0.001	Supported

Source: Authors' compilation.

The p-values and Standardized regression weights (β) for each construct are shown in Table 05. P-Value for all the constructs are coming less than 0.05, which indicates that Hypotheses H1, H2, h3 and H5 are supported. According to β , Mobile Payment ($\beta=0.33$) is the strongest predictors of

Table 07: Mediation Result

Hyp	Relationship	Direct Effect	Indirect Effect	Total Effect	VAF	Results
H4	MP \rightarrow Trust \rightarrow BI	0.586	0.437	1.023	0.427	Partial Mediation

Source: Authors' compilation.

Conclusion and Implication

mobile shopping BI, followed by Shopping Convenience ($\beta=0.19$) and Product Choice ($\beta=0.17$) respectively. Also the result shows that the Behavioural Intention is positively influence the Actual usage of M-Commerce which indicates H5 also supported.

Figure 02. Regression Values of Constructs

Mediation effects can be calculated by measuring direct and indirect effect. According to Hair et al., (2013), the value adjustment factor (VAF) is measured by division of indirect effect by total effect. The Table 06 shows the reference value

Table 06: Mediation Relationship

VAF (in%)	Relationship
<20	No Mediation
20<VAF<80	Partial Mediation
>80	Full Mediation

The value of VAF is 0.427. The results show that trust partially mediates the relationship between mobile payment and behavioural intention. The result indicates that H4 also supported.

The results of the study demonstrate the factors influencing the behavioural intention of online shoppers towards usage of M-Commerce and actual usage. The results are in align with all the previous study results (Wang et al., 2015), (Dong et al., 2012) and (Hossain et al., 2008). The study results can be summarized as identify the factors influencing the usage of M-Commerce empirically in terms of city (Bangalore), population (IT Salaried), area (M-Commerce) and technology used (Smart Phone). The study results can be useful for the app developers and online vendors to identify the factors needs to be considered while their plan.

LIMITATION AND FUTURE SCOPE

The study has few limitations those are, the sample was selected based on non-probabilistic sampling technique and the respondents are salaried IT employees. For generalizing the result, the above precautions needs to be considered. The study was conducted only in Bangalore and the sample was collected for the duration of 3 months. The study can be further extended by testing adding more factors like subjective norm and few more.

REFERENCES

1. Alan C. B. Tse, Frederick Hong Kit Yim and KaHoTse (2003). What Hooks M-Commerce Customers? *Spring 2003*.
2. Al- Sukkar, A., & Hassan, H. (2005). Toward a model for the acceptance of internet banking in developing countries. *Information Technology for Development*, 11 (4), pp. 381- 398.
3. Amoroso, D.L. and Magnier-Watanabe, R. (2012). Building a research model for mobile wallet consumer adoption: the case of mobile Suica in Japan. *Journal of Theoretical and Applied Electronic Commerce Research*. 7 (1), pp. 94-110.
4. Bennet, A., Ward, R.A. and Lee, A.P. (2002). *Applied Management Models*, chapter (3), Vol.: 2, 2nd ed. London: Oxford University Press, pp.63-74.
5. Chaffey, D. (2009). *E-Business and E-Commerce Management: Strategy, Implementation and Practice*, 4th ed. England: Pearson Education Limited.
6. Chong, A.Y.L., Chan, F.T. and Ooi, K.B. (2012). Predicting consumer decisions to adopt mobile commerce: cross-country empirical examination between China and Malaysia. *Decision Support Systems*, 53 (1), pp. 34-43.
7. Chong, A.Y.L. (2013a). A two-staged SEM-neural network approach for understanding and predicting the determinants of m-commerce adoption. *Expert Systems with Applications*, 40 (4), pp. 1240-1247.
8. Chong, A.Y.L. (2013b). Predicting M-Commerce adoption determinants: a neural network approach. *Expert Systems with Applications*, 40 (2), pp. 523-530.
9. David Gefen, Elena Karahanna and Detmar W. Straub (2003). Trust and TAM in Online Shopping: An Integrated Model. *MIS Quarterly*, 27 (1), pp. 51-90
10. Davis, D., and Cosenza, R. (1993). *Business research for decision making*. California: Wadsworth Publishing Company.
11. Gilbert, L.A. and Han, H. (2005), "Understanding mobile data services adoption: demography, attitudes or needs?", *Technological Forecasting & Social Change*, Vol. 72 No. 3, pp. 327-337.
12. Hair, J. F., Ringle, C. M., & Sarstedt, M. (2011). PLS-SEM: Indeed a silver bullet. *Journal of Marketing Theory and Practice*, 19(2), 139–152.

13. Hanafizadeh, P., Behboudi, M., Koshksaray, A.A. and Tabar, M.J.S. (2014), "Mobile-banking adoption by Iranian bank clients", *Telematics and Informatics*, Vol. 31 No. 1, pp. 62-78.
14. Hossain, M.M., and Prybutok, V.R. (2008), "Consumer Acceptance of RFID Technology: An Exploratory Study", *IEEE Transactions on Engineering Management*, Vol. 55, No. 2, pp. 316-328.
15. H Yao, Y Chen, Y Chen, X Zhu (2019), "Mediating Role of Risk Perception of Trust and Contract Enforcement in the Construction Industry", *Journal of Construction Engineering and Management*, Vol. 145, Issue 2 (February 2019)
16. Icolaou, A. I., and D. H. McKnight. 2006. "Perceived information quality in data exchanges: Effects on risk, trust, and intention to use." *Inf. Syst. Res.* 17 (4): 332–351. <https://doi.org/10.1287/isre.1060.0103>.
17. Ikram Dastan and CemGurler (2016), "Factors Affecting the Adoption of Mobile Payment Systems: An Empirical Analysis", *Emerging Market Journal*, Volume 6, No 1
18. Ingham, J., Cadieux, J. and Berrada, A.M. (2015), "E-shopping acceptance: a qualitative and meta-analytic review", *Information & Management*, Vol. 52 No. 1, pp. 44-60.
19. Islam, M.A., Khan, M.A., Ramayah, T. and Hossain, M.M. (2011), "The adoption of mobile commerce service among employed mobile phone users in Bangladesh: self-efficacy as a moderator", *International Business Research*, Vol. 4, No. 2, pp. 80.
20. Je, H. C., & Myeong-Cheol, P. (2005), "Mobile internet acceptance in Korea", *Internet Research*, Vol. 15 No. 2, pp. 125–140.
21. Jiang., Zhilin Yang., and Minjoon Jun. 2013. Measuring consumer perceptions of online shopping convenience. *Journal of Service Management*. Vol. 24 Issue: 2, pp.191-214
22. Karnouskos, S. (2004), "Mobile payment: a journey through existing procedures and standardization initiatives", *Communications Surveys & Tutorials*, Vol. 6, No. 4, pp. 44-66.
23. Kourouthanassis, P.E. and Giaglis, G.M. (2012), "Introduction to the special issue mobile commerce: the past, present, and future of mobile commerce research", *International Journal of Electronic Commerce*, Vol. 16 No. 4, pp. 5-18.
24. Lai, J.-Y., Debbarma, S. and Ulhas, K.R. (2012), "An empirical study of consumer switching behaviour towards mobile shopping: a push-pull-mooring model", *International Journal of Mobile Communications*, Vol. 10 No. 4, pp. 386-404.
25. Laukkanen, T., Sinkkonen, S., Kivijä, M. and Laukkanen, P. (2007), "Innovation resistance among mature consumers", *Journal of Consumer Marketing*, Vol. 24 No. 7, pp. 419-427.
26. Lee, S. A., Johnson, T.S., Ward, J. P. and Jackson, S. (2000). Comparative Study of 3 Management Methods. *International Journal of Business Management*, 36 (4), pp. 232-245.
27. Madhurima Deb, Aarti Agrawal, (2017) "Factors impacting the adoption of m-banking: understanding brand India's potential for financial inclusion", *Journal of Asia Business Studies*, Vol. 11 Issue: 1, pp.22-40, <https://doi.org/10.1108/JABS-11-2015-0191>
28. Mahatanankoon, P. (2007), "The effects of personality traits and optimum stimulation

- level on text-messaging activities and m-commerce intention”, *International Journal of Electronic Commerce*, Vol. 12 No. 1, pp. 7-30.
29. Commerce, Vol. 12 No. 1, pp. 7-30.
30. Min Li, Z.Y., Dong., and Xi Chen. 2012. Factors influencing consumption experience of Mobile Commerce: A study from experiential view. *Internet Research*, Vol. 22 Issue: 2, pp.120-141
31. Nicolaou, A. I., and D. H. McKnight. 2006. “Perceived information quality in data exchanges: Effects on risk, trust, and intention to use”, *Information Systems Research*, Vol. 17 No. 4 pp: 332–351. <https://doi.org/10.1287/isre.1060.0103>.
32. Shin, G. and Shim, S.S.Y. (2002), “A service management framework for m-commerce applications”, *Mobile Networks and Applications*, Vol. 7 No. 3, pp. 199-212.
33. Sreenivasan, J. and Noor, M.N.M. (2010), “A conceptual framework on mobile commerce acceptance and usage among Malaysian consumers: the influence of location, privacy, trust and purchasing power”, *WSEAS Transactions on Information Science and Applications*, Vol. 7 No. 5, pp. 661-670.
34. Stephen Burgess and Stan Karanasios (2008), “Electronic Commerce and Business-to-Consumer (B2C) Relations”, *Journal of Electronic Commerce in Organizations*, Volume 6, Issue 4
35. Tang, J., &Veijalainen, J. (2001). Using Agents to Improve Security and Convenience in Mobile E-Commerce, *Proceedings of the 34th Hawaii International Conference of System Sciences*, IEEE Computer Society Press, LosAlamitos.
36. Torkzadeh and Dhillon (2002), “Measuring Factors that Influence the Success of Internet Commerce”, *Information Systems Research*, Vol. 13, No. 2, June 2002, pp. 187-204
37. Upadhyay, P. and Jahanyan, S. (2016), “Analyzing user perspective on the factors affecting use intention of mobile-based transfer payment”, *Internet Research*, Vol. 26 No. 1, pp. 38-56.
38. Wang, Y., Lin, H., &Luarn, P. (2006), “Predicting consumer intention to use mobile service”, *Information Systems Journal*, 16(2), 157-179.
39. Wang, R. J. H., Malthouse, E. C., & Krishnamurthi, L. (2015). On the go: How mobile shopping affects customer purchase behavior. *Journal of Retailing*, 91(2), 217–234.
40. Wen, C., Prybutok, V.R. and Xu, C. (2011), “An integrated model for customer online repurchase intention”, *Journal of Computer Information Systems*, Vol. 52 No. 1, pp. 14-23.
41. Wong, C.H., Tan, G.W.H., Ooi, K.B. and Lin, B. (2015), “Mobile shopping: the next frontier of the shopping industry? An emerging market perspective”, *International Journal of Mobile Communications*, Vol. 13 No. 1, pp. 92-112.
42. Wong, C.H., Lee, H.S., Lim, Y.H., Chua, B.H., Chai, B.H. and Tan, G.W.H. (2012), “Predicting the consumers’ intention to adopt mobile shopping: an emerging market perspective”, *International Journal of Network and Mobile Technologies*, Vol. 3 No. 4, pp. 24-39.
43. Wu, J.H. and Wang, S.C. (2005), “What drives mobile commerce?: an empirical evaluation of the revised technology acceptance model”, *Information & Management*, Vol. 42 No. 5, pp. 719-729.
44. Wu, J.H., Wang, Y.M. and Tai, W.C. (2004), “Mobile shopping site selection: the consumers’ viewpoint”, *Proceedings of the*

- 37th Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences, Big Island, HI, 5-8 January.
46. Yang, K. and Kim, H.Y. (2012), “Mobile shopping motivation: an application of multiple discriminant analysis”, *International Journal of Retail & Distribution Management*, Vol. 40 No. 10, pp. 778-789.
47. https://economictimes.indiatimes.com/articleshow/62240630.cms?utm_source=contentofinterest&utm_medium=text&utm_campaign=cppst
48. <https://economictimes.indiatimes.com/industry/services/retail/online-retail-consumers-to-cross-100-million-by-2017-assochem-resurgent-india-study/articleshow/56417797.cms>
49. <https://main.trai.gov.in/release-publication/reports/telecom-subscriptions-reports>
50. <https://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/business/india-business/india-top-ranked-country-in-mobile-data-consumption-amitabh-kant/articleshow/62203927.cms>
51. <https://www.internetworldstats.com/top20.htm>